

In-Silico Molecular Docking, HPTLC Study and Unveiling the Biological Activities of Geum Urbanum L. Plant Extracts: Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Cancer Activities

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ABSTRACT

Geum urbanum is well known for its many therapeutic uses. In the past, it was used to treat oral and skin diseases as well as digestive problems like diarrhea, dyspepsia, constipation, indigestion, stomach issues, and appetite loss. The aim of the research is to explore the phytoconstituents on the basis of in-silico molecular docking, HPTLC, anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer activity of the extracts using in-vitro study. Molecular docking of gallic acid was performed against target proteins MAPK, Braf, P53, PD1, COX 2. Extracts were prepared by traditional (Maceration) and novel techniques (Ultrasound assisted extraction and Microwave assisted extraction). The preliminary phytochemical screening was performed for qualitative analysis and High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) was performed for the quantitative analysis of phytoconstituent. Hyaluronidase inhibition assay and Human Red Blood Cell membrane stabilization assay were used for the evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity. The in-vitro anti-cancer activity of extracts was evaluated by MTT assay using A431 cell line. The docking score of Gallic acid was found -7.78913 against Braf. The percentage yield of extracts was 6.625±0.5% w/w (minimum) in maceration and 12.75±0.02% w/w (maximum) in MAE for ethyl acetate extract. Gallic acid found maximum in Mac extract 10.38% by HPTLC. The maximum percentage of inhibition 52.22±4.1% in Hyaluronidase assay and 99.14±0.32% in HRBC assay was observed at higher concentration. The IC₅₀ value of mac. extract was found to be 74.41 µg/ml and IC₅₀ of UAE, MAE extracts were 71.19 µg/ml and 138.19 µg/ml.

Keywords: Gallic acid, HPTLC, docking, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory activity

INTRODUCTION

The genus Geum, also referred to as "Avens" contains 70 species belongs to the family Rosaceae (1). This herbaceous perennial plant species, often known as wood avens. A plant with an erect, hairy, branched shrub with three-lobed, greyish leaves and tiny, yellow flowers with five petals. The roots are spicy and fragrant, and the seeds are spherical, brown and stinging. It is sold commercially in the market as a dried herb (roots or aerial parts). It enhances the flavour of fruit pies, stewed fruit, soups, broths, stews and sauces. The chemical compositions of Geum species includes the presence of terpenes, sterols, and flavonoids, along with trace amounts of essential oil. The plant has volatile oil, sesquiterpene lactone (cnicin), carotenoids, flavonoids, tannins (10.5%), phenolic compounds (gallic, caffeic, chlorogenic

acids, and eugenol), and vicianose sugar (2). In traditional herbal medicine, the roots and rhizomes have been used to treat a variety of diseases, including oral diseases like throat and mouth infections, skin conditions like chilblains and hemorrhoids, and gastrointestinal disorders like diarrhea, dyspepsia, constipation, indigestion, stomach upsets, and appetite loss. It shows anti-bacterial (3), neuroprotective (4), anti-microbial (5), anti-oxidant (6), anti-parkinson (7) activity. The objective of this research was to evaluate the anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties.

Material and Methods:

Materials: Ethyl acetate, distilled water, chloroform, diethylamine, methanol, Millon's reagent ferric chloride, Fehling's solution A and Solution B, benedict's reagent, Mayer's test, Wagner's test,

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chloroform, DMSO, sodium Phosphate Buffer, calcium chloride, hyaluronic acid solution, Albumin serum, sodium acetate, Quercetin, Alsever solution, isosaline solution, sodium phosphate buffer, diclofenac sodium, Hyaluronidase injection IP 1500 IU (Shreya Life Sciences Pvt. Ltd.), procured from Central Drug House Pvt. Ltd and Fluka, Fetal Bovine Serum(Gibco), MTT Reagent, D-PBS, Doxorubicin were procured from Sigma aldrich.

Plant collection and authentication

The dried roots of *Geum urbanum* were obtained from IHERBA Ltd. England, UK in January 2025. The roots were identified and authenticated by Dr. K. Madhava Chetty from Sri Venkateswara University Tirupati, A. P. on the basis of macroscopic studies with authentication No. 0371.

Molecular Docking

Preparation of Proteins

The structures of COX-2 (PDB:5GMN), MAPK (PDB:17GS), Braf (PDB:5ITA), P53 (PDB:4A9Z), PD1(PDB:6KOY) target for proteins were obtained from protein data Bank (www.rcsb.org). For docking studies, all ligands were removed out of the protein binding sites. All (ligands) were removed from the binding sites of proteins for docking studies (8).

Preparation of ligands

Bioactive compounds identified from *G. urbanum* in previous literatures were selected as ligands for docking study. The 3-D structures of the ligands β -D fructose, tormentic- acid, gallic acid, succinic-acid, catechin, caeffic acid, ellagic acid, ellagic acid pentoside, cholrogenic acid were collected from pub chem database. These structures were saved in SDF file format.

Protein Ligand docking

Docking was performed by using Schrodinger software. The receptor grid was generated between the prepared protein and ligand and run for docking.

Maceration

50gm powdered roots of *G. urbanum* were macerated in 500ml ethyl acetate at room temperature for 72hrs and the crude ethyl acetate extract was concentrated in a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure and the residue was collected (9).

Ultrasound Assisted Extraction

The extraction was executed in a probe sonicator with 37 kHz frequency, with an adjustable time and temperature. The powdered root was kept in direct contact with ultrasonic waves 37 kHz, solid to solvent ratio 37.25 gm/ml for 20 min at 25°C. The obtained extract was filtered with the Whatman filter paper and the filtrate was concentrated by rotary evaporator. Finally, the residues were collected (10).

Microwave Assisted Extraction

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) was performed using an microwave (CEM)1g powder of roots of *G. urbanum* was microwaved with ethyl acetate at a 1:7 ratio, power 160W and temperature 50°C for 10 min. After the microwave treatment, the *G. urbanum* extract was filtered and supernatant was concentrated by rotary evaporator at 50°C and lyophilized (11).

Preliminary phytochemical Screening:

The extracts of *G. urbanum* prepared by different extraction techniques were subjected for qualitative phytochemical analysis. These identification test were performed to determine the presence of Phytochemicals like carbohydrates, proteins, Phenols and tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids and steroids (12).

High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography:

Preparation of standard solution of gallic acid:

5mg of gallic acid was put into a 100ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 50ml of methanol to prepare a stock solution of gallic acid (50 μ g/ml). To obtain stock solution of 50 μ g/mL, it was sonicated for 10 min. and the final volume make up to 100 mL with methanol.

Preparation of sample

10 mg of *G. urbanum* root extracts prepared by (maceration, UAE and MAE) were transferred in to a

100 mL volumetric flask by dissolving in 70 mL methanol. To prepare a stock solution of 1.00 mg/mL, the final volume of the solutions was made up to 100 mL using methanol. Different volume of stock solution 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 of gallic acid were spotted on TLC plate.

Silica gel Merck plates containing silica gel 60 F254 TLC plates were used for HPTLC analysis. Using a CAMAG Linomat 5 sample applicator, standard gallic acid solutions and extract made by maceration, UAE, and MAE were applied to TLC plates. The plate was developed for 20 minutes at room temperature in

a CAMAG twin-trough vertical development chamber that was saturated with toluene, ethyl acetate, and formic acid (4.5:5.5:0.5 v/v) (13). It was then dried for 5 min. The front position of the solvent was fixed at 80 mm. The plate was analyzed using a CAMAG visualizer 2 with a tungsten light source (366 nm) and Vision CATS software (3.2.23095.1). Retardation factor (Rf) values were compared with the standard to validate the presence of gallic acid in *G. urbanum* crude extracts (14). The image was captured in UV light, at 274 nm and 366nm as given in "Fig. 2" and Fig. 3".

Fig. 2 : HPTLC chromatogram visualized under UV at 276nm

Fig. 3: HPTLC chromatogram visualized under UV at 366nm

In-vitro anti-inflammatory activity

Hyaluronidase inhibition assay:

5mg of plant extracts were dissolved in 250 μ L of dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). The samples were prepared in sodium phosphate buffer (200M, pH 7) at varying concentrations of 100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 μ g/mL. The sample solution (25 μ L) had been mixed with hyaluronidase (4U/mL, 100 μ L) and incubated for 30 min. at 37°C. The hyaluronic acid solution of substrate (0.03% in 300M sodium

phosphate, pH 5.4, 100L), was added for reaction initiation. It was then incubated for 45 minutes at 37°C. An acid albumin solution (0.1% bovine serum albumin in 24 mM sodium acetate, pH 3.8, 1 mL) was used to precipitate the undigested hyaluronic acid. Absorbance was measured at 600 nm following a 10-minute incubation period at room temperature. When the enzyme was absent, the absorbance measurement served as a control value for maximum inhibition. Using either quercetin or indomethacin as a positive control, the test was performed three times (15). The

percentage of inhibition was calculated with the given formula:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{\text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \times 100$$

HRBC ASSAY

2ml of Alsever solution were mixed with 2ml of human blood. After centrifuging the mixture for 20 minutes at 1500 rpm two times, three isosaline solutions were used to wash the packed cells. A 10% v/v isosaline solution was made using the measured blood volume. one milliliter of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4, 0.15M) was taken in a test tube. 0.5 ml of plant extracts, 2 ml of hypo saline (0.36%), 0.5 ml of HRBC solution (10% v/v), and various concentration of standard diclofenac sodium (100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 µg/ml) were added to different test tubes. A spectrophotometer was used to calculate the percentage of hemolysis at 560nm (16). The percentage of hemolysis of RBC was determined by the given formula:

$$\text{Percentage of hemolysis} = \frac{\text{absorbance of test sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Anti-cancer activity

MTT assay: Seed 200 microliters of cell suspension at the appropriate cell density (15,000 cells per well) in

a 96-well plate and let the cells develop for approximately 24 hours. Incubate the plate for 24 hours at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ environment after adding the proper amounts of the specified test chemicals diluted in culture media. The plates are removed from the incubator after incubation. The spent media is removed, and MTT reagent is added until the final concentration is 0.5 mg/ml of total volume. Cover it with aluminum foil to prevent light exposure. The MTT reagent remove from the plates after 3hrs incubation and add 100µl of solubilization solution (DMSO). An ELISA reader or spectrophotometer used to measure the absorbance at 570 nm. % Cell viability was determined with the given formula:

$$\% \text{ cell viability} = \frac{\text{Mean abs of treated cells}}{\text{Mean abs of Untreated cells}} \times 100.$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Molecular docking:

The molecular docking study of gallic acid was performed against Cyclooxygenase enzyme 2 (COX-2) (PDB ID: 5GMN), Braf(5ITA), P53(4A9Z) MAPK and PD1(6KOY). Gallic acid showed best docking score against 5ITA among 17GS, 5ITA, 4A9Z, 6KOY and 5GMN (Table 1). 2D interaction of gallic acid with 5ITA is given in Fig. 1.

Table 1: Docking results of Gallic acid with Braf (5ITA), PD1(6KOY), P53(4A9Z), MAPK(17GS), Cox-2(5GMN)

Compound	CID	PDB ID	Docking Score
Gallic acid	60253	5ITA	-7.78913
		6KOY	-6.98536
		4A9Z	-4.93172
		17GS	-6.97684
		5GMN	-6.74098

Fig. 1: 2D interaction of gallic acid with 5HTA

Percentage Yield of extracts of *G. urbanum*: The percentage yield of ethyl acetate extracts prepared by maceration, UAE and MAE are given in **Table 2**. The

percentage yield was found minimum (6.625±0.5% w/w) in maceration and maximum in MAE (12.75±0.02) extract.

Table 2: %age yield of extract

Sr. No.	Extraction	%age Yield (w/w)
1	Maceration	6.625±0.5
2	UAE	12.5±1.0
3	MAE	12.75±0.02

Phytochemical screening:

The phytochemical screening showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, phenols and tannins and absence of proteins, carbohydrates and terpenoids in the ethyl acetate root extract given in

Table 3. The preliminary phytochemical analysis gives an idea about the presence and absence of primary and secondary metabolites present in drug.

Table 3: Identification test of extracts

Sr. No.	Chemical constituents	Identification test	Maceration	UAE	MAE
1.	Proteins	Millon’s Test	-	-	-
2.	Carbohydrates	Fehling’s Test	+	+	+
		Benedict’s Test	+	+	+
3.	Phenols and Tannins	Ferric chloride Test	+	+	+
4.	Alkaloids	Mayer’s Test	+	+	+
		Wagner’s test	+	+	+

5.	Terpenoids	Salkowski test	-	-	-
6.	Flavonoids	Ferric chloride test	+	+	+
7.	Steroid test	Salkowski test	-	-	-

+ = present, - = absent

HPTLC:

Quantitative estimation of gallic acid in *G. urbanum* by HPTLC:

The ethyl acetate extract prepared by maceration exhibited four peaks indicating the presence of four different components with R_f values and have % area ranging from 17.39-50.38%. The extract prepared by UAE and MAE exhibited 4 peaks indicating the presence of at least 4 different component with R_f values have % area ranging from 28.19-34.54% and 19.26-47.08%. The component gallic acid in the standard “Fig. 4” and sample “Fig. 5, 6, and 7” extracts was determined to have an R_f value of (0.356). Calibration curve was plotted against the

peak area graph and the gallic acid concentration in revealed a linear relationship; from the “Fig. 8” an equation of linear regression was obtained. Amount of gallic acid was calculated by the equation in three extracts that is maceration, UAE and MAE. The concentration of gallic acid in *G. urbanum* root extracts was found maximum (6.31 µg) in MAE extract and minimum in UAE (6.14 µg) respectively. 3D densitogram of standard and extracts at 254 and 366 nm are given in “Fig. 9”. 3D densitogram of gallic acid and extracts were compared. Quantitative amount of gallic acid present in the extracts is shown in Table 4.

Fig. 4: HPTLC chromatogram of Gallic acid extract at 254 nm

Fig 5: HPTLC chromatogram of Mac at 254 nm

Fig. 6: HPTLC chromatogram of

Fig. 7: HPTLC chromatogram of

UAE extract at 254nm

MAE extract at 254nm

Fig. 8: Calibration curve for of gallic acid

Fig. 9: 3D densitogram of Gallic acid in all tracks (standard and extracts) at absorbance 275 nm

Table 4: Comparison of gallic acid in different extract

Sr. No	Extraction method	Vol.	Rf value	Quantity (gallic acid)
1.	Mac	10 μ l	0.356	6.3 μ g/ml
2.	UAE	10 μ l	0.365	6.14 μ g/ml
3.	MAE	10 μ l	0.357	6.31 μ g/ml

Anti-inflammatory:

Hyaluronidase inhibition assay: The evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of the extracts was done by Hyaluronidase inhibition assay. The percentage inhibition of standard and extracts at concentration

range 100-500 μ g/ml are given in Table 5. The MAE extract possessed maximum percentage of hyaluronidase inhibition 53.7 \pm 2.3% as compared to standard 26.75 \pm 2.4%. Effect of *G. urbanum* extracts on %age inhibition is given in "Fig. 10"

Table 5 : *In vitro* anti-inflammatory activity of *G. urbanum* extract by Hyaluronidase inhibition assay

Con. (µg/ml)	Std. (%)	Mac	UAE	MAE
100	16.75±0.7	15.18±2.3	23.33±0.6	20.92±0.14
200	19.75±1.9	20.92±3.7	31.23±1.6	23.14±0.88
300	20.5±2.2	27.96±3.6	32.4±2.7	29.25±2.2
400	22.25±1.2	41.48±4.4	36.29±1.9	36.66±3.2
500	26.75±2.4	52.22±4.1	42.42±0.7	53.7±2.3

Fig. 10: Effect of *G. urbanum* extracts on %age inhibition**HRBC Assay:**

The HRBC membrane stabilization test was used to assess the anti-inflammatory effect of extracts in comparison to standard diclofenac. The extract (UAE)

exhibited maximum percentage inhibition of hemolysis/stabilization of blood cell 99.14±0.32% compared to diclofenac 98.65±0.03% at concentration of 500µg/ml **Table 6**. Effect of *G. urbanum* extracts on %age inhibition of hemolysis is given in “**Fig. 11**”.

Table 6: *In-vitro* anti-inflammatory activity of *G. urbanum* extract by HRBC

Conc.(µg/ml)	Mac	UAE	MAE	Std.
100	97.29±0.03	47.58±0.23	92.96±0.89	96.16±0.38
200	97.45±0.022	96.42±0.12	92.87±0.36	96.33±0.28
300	98.84±0.014	97.02±0.18	96.98±0.87	97.64±0.67
400	99.16±0.013	97.48±0.23	97.02±0.46	98.32±0.01
500	99.50±0.12	99.14±0.32	97.28±0.47	98.65±0.03

Fig. 11: Effect of *G. urbanum* extracts on %age inhibition of haemolysis

Anti-cancer:

MTT assay:

The molecular mechanism behind the extracts' in vitro cytotoxic effects was determined using the MTT assay (17). Five different concentrations of extracts (20 µg/ml, 40 µg/ml, 60 µg/ml, 80 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml) were taken for the determination of IC₅₀ value. The viability of A431 cells decreases with increase in extract concentration. The effect of cell viability on concentrations of UAE *G. urbanum* is given in **Table 7**. IC₅₀ value of mac extract has been found to be 74.41 µg/ml and UAE, MAE extracts were found 71.19 µg/ml and 138.19 µg/ml. The morphology of A431 cells treated by different

concentrations of *G. urbanum* UAE after 24hrs incubation is shown in “**Fig. 12**”.

Table 7 : Percentage cell viability of A431 cells treated with different concentrations of UAE *G. Urbanum*

Culture condition	% cell viability
Untreated	100
Doxorubicin-1ug	64.12
UAE G U-20ug	90.43
UAE G U-40ug	78.03
UAE G U-60ug	58.63
UAE G U-80ug	41.12
UAE G U-100ug	27.41

Fig. 12: A431 cells treated by different concentrations of *G. urbanum* UAE after the incubation period of 24hrs

Discussion: Molecular docking study gives an idea about the binding of ligand (gallic -acid) with the different receptors. The “**Fig. 1**” indicates how gallic acid binds within the active site Braf (PDB ID: 5ITA)

protein. Gallic acid shows strong hydrogen bonding due to its multiple hydroxyl groups. It forms a stable complex with 5ITA primarily through Hydrogen bonds (dominant) and minor hydrophobic

interactions. Gallic acid showed maximum docking score -7.78913. This suggests good binding affinity, which may relate to its biological activity such as anti-inflammatory or anticancer effects. The extracts were prepared by different extraction methods like maceration, UAE and MAE. The results indicate that modern extraction method MAE gives maximum percentage yield in comparison to maceration. Hence, we can say that modern extraction methods are better than the conventional methods. The preliminary phytochemical study of extracts showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, phenols and tannins. The gallic acid was quantitatively determined by HPTLC. The quantity of gallic acid was found maximum in MAE extract. Higher the amount of gallic acid in extract higher will be the anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer activity of the plant. The anti-inflammatory activity of the prepared extracts was evaluated by Hyaluronidase inhibition assay and HRBC assay. The MAE extract possessed maximum percentage of hyaluronidase inhibition $53.7 \pm 2.3\%$ as compared to standard $26.75 \pm 2.4\%$. It is known that hyaluronidase plays a role in inflammation and allergic responses. Hence, hyaluronidase enzyme inhibition will significantly produce anti-inflammatory effect. The extract (UAE) exhibited maximum percentage inhibition of hemolysis/stabilization of blood cell $99.14 \pm 0.32\%$ compared to diclofenac $98.65 \pm 0.03\%$. Hemoglobin absorbance was measured using the HRBC membrane stabilization technique. Hemoglobin is released as a result of membrane lyses because the RBC membrane has lesser stability. The MTT assay was utilized for the identification of molecular mechanism behind the extracts *in-vitro* cytotoxic effects. As the concentration of extract increases with viability of A431 cells decreases. IC_{50} value of mac extract has been found to be $74.41 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and UAE, MAE extracts were found $71.19 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $138.19 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Hence, we can say that UAE extract showed minimum IC_{50} value. It indicates higher potency and efficacy.

Relationship between phytochemicals and observed activity:

GA effect on cancer:

On A375S2 human melanoma cells, the GA significantly inhibited cell growth and induced apoptosis. Cell proliferation declined in a timely and dose-dependent way after gallic acid treatment. Proapoptotic B-cell lymphoma 2 (Bcl-Fp132) associated X protein (Bax) is upregulated and antiapoptotic Bcl-2 is downregulated in the apoptosis molecular process. GA caused the release of cytochrome c, which encouraged the activation of caspase 9 and 3 and finally apoptosis by reducing the mitochondrial membrane potential in a time-dependent manner (18).

Gallic acid effect on inflammation:

Gallic acid inhibits NF- κ B as well as MAPK signaling, further reduces effector capacities and immune cell activation, which have an effect on the cytokines that decreases inflammation (19). In animals with a condition resembling psoriasis, gallic acid has been demonstrated to prevent interactions between interleukin (IL)-17 and IL-17 receptors (20). Gallic acid decreases the generation of IL-17 from nasal and colon tissue in animal models of rhinitis and ulcerative colitis (21,22).

CONCLUSION:

G. urbanum demonstrated anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer activity. The ethyl acetate extracts (mac, UAE and MAE) were subjected for the quantitative analysis of gallic acid. It gives an idea about the concentration of gallic acid present in the extracts. Gallic acid showed best docking score -7.78913 against Braf receptor and indicated the better binding affinity. The UAE extracts exhibited significant anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties. So, from both docking and different in-vitro studies we can say that the plant compounds may possess important biological properties.

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